

The Influence of Salesforce Management Systems on the Orientation, Support Beliefs, and Capabilities of Account Managers at PT. Hilti Nusantara

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ABSTRACT: Digital transformation in the construction sector can be a major catalyst for increasing productivity. Since 2023, Hilti Nusantara has adopted the use of Customer Relationship Management (CRM) from the previous BYD system to Salesforce with the aim of overcoming challenges in improving the operational efficiency of account managers and also deepening customer relationship management in the construction world. The use of Salesforce has not yet been implemented optimally, as the actual target for account managers of four customer visits per day has only reached an average of 2.6 visits per day. This study aims to conduct an in-depth analysis of the impact of Salesforce implementation at PT. Hilti Nusantara, as well as how these factors influence account manager performance. This study uses a survey method to collect data through a questionnaire. Sampling was conducted using a non-probability method with a purposive sampling approach. The sample in this study consisted of 51 respondents who are account managers at Hilti Nusantara. This study uses SPSS 26 application as an auxiliary tool.

KEYWORDS: Customer Relationship Management, Efisiensi, Salesforce

INTRODUCTION

Digitalization in the construction sector is becoming increasingly important given that the era of construction 4.0 is important as a trigger for construction development and new economic growth. Digital transformation in the construction sector can be a key driver for achieving productivity improvements [1]. Additionally, the adoption of digital technology in the construction sector can increase productivity by up to 14-15% and accelerate project completion by approximately 20%. This is primarily related to reducing manual errors and optimizing project resources [2]. Hilti Indonesia, through its entity PT Hilti Nusantara, as one of the main players in this sector, needs to ensure that its digital transformation not only improves internal efficiency but also has a direct impact on customer satisfaction and loyalty.

Since 2023, Hilti Nusantara has adopted the use of Customer Relationship Management (CRM) from the previous BYD system to Salesforce. This step was taken with the aim of overcoming challenges in improving operational efficiency from the account manager side and also deepening customer relationship management in the construction world. Salesforce, known as an integrated platform, offers several features that can improve operational efficiency, such as pipeline management, task automation, and sales lead management [3]. From December 2023 to the present, Hilti has experienced fairly good sales growth, but some account managers still encounter unstructured sales lead and pipeline management.

CRM systems have been proven to have a positive impact on sales performance. Research shows that mCRM enables collaboration between account managers and company management as a whole to view each other's interactions with customers in real time. Quick access to customer data allows for more efficient solutions in deciding on prospects and sales opportunities [4].

On the other hand, CRM technology can improve sales process behaviors such as creating and managing business opportunities. Studies show that CRM not only helps in creating opportunities but can also enhance the effectiveness of managing customer relationships sustainably [5]. By automating various processes such as prospect tracking and sales pipeline management, Salesforce enables account managers to focus on more valuable interactions with customers, resulting in increased customer satisfaction and loyalty [5]. Salesforce is expected to strengthen account managers' orientation, build their confidence in the system support provided by both the organization and supervisors, and enhance their capabilities in achieving business targets. This digital transformation reflects an industry trend that increasingly relies on technology to improve the productivity and effectiveness of sales teams.

Orientation refers to the extent to which an account manager understands and applies sales strategies that focus on customers, long-term relationships, and effectiveness in achieving sales targets. With the use of Salesforce, it is expected that there will be an improvement in this orientation because the system provides data-driven insights, facilitates the recording of customer interactions, and assists in more structured strategy planning. However, the adoption of new systems often faces challenges in the form of user resistance and varying learning processes among account managers at Hilti Nusantara.

Account managers' confidence in the support provided by management, both as an organization and from supervisors, greatly influences their motivation and productivity. If account managers believe that Salesforce truly provides benefits, such as easy access to customer information, data-driven strategy recommendations, and better integration within the sales team, they will be more motivated to utilize it to its fullest potential. However, it was found that the newly adopted CRM system was too complex, so the productivity of Hilti Nusantara account managers was highly dependent on management to provide support during the initial transition period of this system change.

Account managers' capabilities include their ability to understand customer needs, develop effective sales strategies, and execute sales with the right approach. With the implementation of Salesforce, it is hoped that account managers will be able to identify business opportunities more quickly, segment customers more effectively, and improve service quality. However, the success of the implementation also depends on the adaptive and analytical capabilities of Hilti Nusantara account managers in processing customer data to support data-driven decision-making.

With these changes, it is important to understand how Salesforce Management Systems truly contribute to improving orientation, confidence in the system, and the capabilities of account managers. This study will examine in depth the impact of Salesforce implementation at PT. Hilti Nusantara, as well as how these factors affect the performance of account managers.

A. Research Objectives

1. How does the use of the Salesforce Management System affect the selling orientation of account managers at Hilti Nusantara?
2. How does the Salesforce Management System affect the improvement of customer orientation by account managers at Hilti Nusantara?
3. How does perceived organizational support affect the successful implementation of the Salesforce Management System at Hilti Nusantara?
4. How does perceived supervisor support affect the effectiveness of the Salesforce Management System at Hilti Nusantara?
5. How does the Salesforce Management System support account managers' ability to adapt their selling techniques in their daily activities?
6. How does the Salesforce Management System enhance the analytical skills of account managers at Hilti Nusantara?

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Customer Relationship Management Theory

CRM encompasses various practices, strategies, and technologies that companies use to manage and analyze customer interactions and data throughout the customer lifecycle, with the aim of strengthening service relationships, retaining customers, and increasing sales [6]. Furthermore, the theory of CRM as a continuous process consisting of four main steps: acquiring knowledge, designing market strategies, interacting with customers, and analyzing customer information. These steps help companies optimize the use of customer data for better decision-making in order to enhance the customer experience [7].

B. Digital Transformation Theory

Digital transformation is not merely about improving business processes, but also fundamentally changing a company's value proposition and strategic direction [8]. This transformation is the main driver of a company's adaptive capabilities, particularly in terms of focusing on customer needs and leveraging technology. Digital transformation is a process that encourages organizations to respond strategically through the use of digital technologies such as information, computing, and communication. This process changes the structure, boundaries, and value creation pathways within a company, as well as bringing about evolution within the business entity itself [9].

C. Employee Performance Theory

Employee performance is influenced by the interaction between individual abilities, motivation, and the work environment. Therefore, optimal employee performance can be measured when these three factors are achieved [10].

D. The Theory of CRM Effectiveness

The effectiveness of CRM depends on the extent to which organizations can integrate technology, processes, and human resources to provide sustainable value for customers and businesses. The effectiveness of CRM is often measured through increased customer loyalty, satisfaction, and financial profits for the company. Payne also emphasizes the importance of strategic orientation in CRM implementation to ensure that CRM solutions not only meet operational needs but also support the company's long-term goals.

E. The Theory of Perceived Organizational Support

States Perceived Organizational Support in his theory that when employees feel that the organization values their contributions and cares about their well-being, they tend to show higher commitment, increased job satisfaction, and better performance. POS encompasses employees' perceptions of the extent to which the organization provides emotional support, recognition for achievements, and the resources needed to achieve work goals [11]. Employees with high perceptions of organizational support are more motivated to respond with high performance, additional initiative, and loyalty to the company. POS also strengthens positive working relationships between employees and their supervisors, thereby creating a work environment conducive to personal and organizational growth [12].

F. The Theory of Customer Orientation

Customer Orientation refers to a company philosophy that focuses on understanding and meeting customer needs to create added value [13]. It is said that organizations with a high customer orientation tend to be more successful in building long-term relationships with customers. Furthermore, highlights the importance of customer orientation in creating a superior customer experience [14].

METHOD

This study uses a deductive approach in developing the theory used. The researcher starts from existing and generally accepted theories, namely customer relationship management theory, to explain the sales force management system in terms of orientation, supporting beliefs, and account manager capabilities at PT. Hilti Nusantara. A quantitative research methodology is used in this study. This quantitative method was chosen because it is suitable for testing specific hypotheses. The population in this study involves all account managers at PT. Hilti Nusantara who use Salesforce and CRM in their daily sales activities. This study uses linear regression analysis using SPSS 26.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Validity Test

Table 1. Validity Test Results

Variable	Item	r-count	r-table (n=51)	Description
<i>Outcome-based Control Systems</i>	OCS1	0,877	0,275	Valid
	OCS2	0,834	0,275	Valid
	OCS3	0,878	0,275	Valid
	OCS4	0,836	0,275	Valid
<i>Activity-based Control Systems</i>	ACS1	0,932	0,275	Valid
	ACS2	0,928	0,275	Valid
	ACS3	0,917	0,275	Valid
	ACS4	0,944	0,275	Valid
<i>Capability-based Control Systems</i>	CCS1	0,880	0,275	Valid
	CCS2	0,907	0,275	Valid
	CCS3	0,886	0,275	Valid

	CCS4	0,936	0,275	Valid
<i>Selling Orientation</i>	SO1	0,819	0,275	Valid
	SO2	0,807	0,275	Valid
	SO3	0,872	0,275	Valid
	SO4	0,877	0,275	Valid
	SO5	0,877	0,275	Valid
<i>Customer Orientation</i>	CO1	0,919	0,275	Valid
	CO2	0,920	0,275	Valid
	CO3	0,911	0,275	Valid
	CO4	0,893	0,275	Valid
	CO5	0,897	0,275	Valid
<i>Perceived Organizational Support</i>	POS1	0,929	0,275	Valid
	POS2	0,913	0,275	Valid
	POS3	0,915	0,275	Valid
	POS4	0,947	0,275	Valid
	POS5	0,899	0,275	Valid
	POS6	0,901	0,275	Valid
	POS7	0,926	0,275	Valid
<i>Perceived Supervisor Support</i>	PSS1	0,868	0,275	Valid
	PSS2	0,872	0,275	Valid
	PSS3	0,864	0,275	Valid
	PSS4	0,859	0,275	Valid
	PSS5	0,900	0,275	Valid
	PSS6	0,855	0,275	Valid
	PSS7	0,860	0,275	Valid
<i>Adaptive Selling</i>	AS1	0,833	0,275	Valid
	AS2	0,878	0,275	Valid
	AS3	0,889	0,275	Valid
	AS4	0,822	0,275	Valid
	AS5	0,886	0,275	Valid
<i>Analytical Skill Encgancement</i>	ASE1	0,833	0,275	Valid
	ASE2	0,885	0,275	Valid
	ASE3	0,873	0,275	Valid

B. Reliability Test

Table 2. Reliability Test

Variable	Cronbach Alpha	Description
<i>Outcome-based Control Systems</i>	0,88	Accepted
<i>Activity-based Control Systems</i>	0,95	Accepted
<i>Capability-based Control Systems</i>	0,92	Accepted
<i>Selling Orientation</i>	0,90	Accepted
<i>Customer Orientation</i>	0,95	Accepted
<i>Perceived Organizational Support</i>	0,97	Accepted
<i>Perceived Supervisor Support</i>	0,94	Accepted

<i>Adaptive Selling</i>	0,91	Accepted
<i>Analytical Skill Encancement</i>	0,83	Accepted

C. Classical Assumption Test

Table 3. Normality Test

<i>Model (N=51)</i>	<i>KS Statistic test</i>	<i>Asym Sig. (2-tailed)</i>
OCSxACS >> SO	0,10	0,20
OCSxACS >>CO	0,13	0,05
OCSxACS >>POS	0,07	0,20
OCSxACS >>PSS	0,06	0,20
CCS>>AS	0,12	0,05
CCS>>ASE	0,10	0,20

Table 4. Multicollinearity Test

<i>Model</i>	<i>Variabel</i>	<i>VIF</i>	<i>Collinearity</i>
OCSxACS >> SO	OCS	1	1
	ACS	1	1
OCSxACS >>CO	OCS	1	1
	ACS	1	1
OCSxACS >>POS	OCS	1	1
	ACS	1	1
OCSxACS >>PSS	OCS	1	1
	ACS	1	1
CCS>>AS	CCS	1	1
CCS>>ASE	CCS	1	1

Table 5. Autocorrelation Test

<i>Model</i>	<i>Durbin Watson</i>
OCSxACS >> SO	2,21
OCSxACS >>CO	1,63
OCSxACS >>POS	2,13
OCSxACS >>PSS	2,00
CCS>>AS	2,03
CCS>>ASE	2,16

Figure 1. Heteroscedasticity Test

D. Hypothesis Test

1. Hypothesis 1

Table 6. Hypothesis 1

	<i>R-Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig</i>
<i>SO</i>	0,50	24,31	0,00

The results of regression analysis on the model of the influence of outcome-based control systems and activity-based control systems on selling orientation found an R-square value of 0.50, meaning that 25% of the selling orientation variable is explained by this model. The F value in this model is 24.31 with a significance value of 0.00. The outcome-based control system and activity-based control system models on selling orientation have a significant influence.

Table 7. Hypothesis 1

	β	<i>T</i>	<i>P-Value</i>
<i>OCS >> SO</i>	0,76	6,95	0,00
<i>ACS >> SO</i>	0,08	0,69	0,49

Based on the regression analysis results, the β , T, and P-Value values were also found in this model. The outcome-based control system variable has a significant effect on selling orientation ($\beta = 0.76$, T = 6.95, and P-Value = 0.00). Meanwhile, no significant

effect of the activity-based control system variable on selling orientation was found. This means that H1 is supported. The outcome-based control system variable has a greater effect than the activity-based control system variable on selling orientation.

2. Hypothesis 2

Table 8. Hypothesis 2

	<i>R-Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig</i>
<i>CO</i>	0,30	10,26	0,00

The results of regression analysis on the model of the influence of outcome-based control systems and activity-based control systems on customer orientation found an R-square value of 0.30, meaning that 9% of the customer orientation variable is explained by this model. The F value in this model is 10.26 with a significance value of 0.00. The outcome-based control system and activity-based control system models on customer orientation have a significant influence.

Table 9. Hypothesis 2

	β	<i>T</i>	<i>P-Value</i>
<i>OCS >> CO</i>	0,10	0,90	0,37
<i>ACS >> CO</i>	0,50	4,46	0,00

Based on the regression analysis results, the β , T, and P-Value values were also found in this model. The outcome-based control system variable does not have a significant effect on customer orientation. Meanwhile, the activity-based control system was found to have a significant effect on customer orientation ($\beta = 0.50$, T = 4.46, and P-Value = 0.00). This means that H2 is supported. The activity-based control system variable has a greater effect than the outcome-based control system on customer orientation.

3. Hypothesis 3

Table 10. Hypothesis 3

	<i>R-Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig</i>
<i>CO</i>	0,30	10,26	0,00

The results of regression analysis on the model of the influence of outcome-based control systems and activity-based control systems on perceived organizational support found an R-square value of 0.94, meaning that 88% of the perceived organizational support variable is explained by this model. The F value in this model is 368.09 with a significance value of 0.00. The outcome-based control system and activity-based control system models on perceived organizational support have a significant influence.

Table 11. Hypothesis 3

	β	<i>T</i>	<i>P-Value</i>
<i>OCS >> POS</i>	-0,02	-0,69	0,49
<i>ACS >> POS</i>	0,95	27,10	0,00

Based on the regression analysis results, the β , T, and P-Value values were also found in this model. The outcome-based control system variable did not have a significant effect on perceived organizational support. However, the activity-based control system was found to have a significant effect on perceived organizational support ($\beta = 0.95$, T = 27.10, and P-Value = 0.00). This means that H3 is supported. The activity-based control system variable has a greater effect than the outcome-based control system on perceived organizational support.

4. Hypothesis 4

Table 12. Hypothesis 4

	<i>R-Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig</i>
<i>PSS</i>	0,48	21,99	0,00

The results of regression analysis on the model of the influence of outcome-based control systems and activity-based control systems on perceived supervisor support found an R-square value of 0.48, meaning that 23% of the perceived supervisor support variable is explained by this model. The F value in this model is 21.99 with a significance value of 0.00. The outcome-based control system and activity-based control system models on perceived supervisor support have a significant influence.

Table 13. Hypothesis 3

	β	<i>T</i>	<i>P-Value</i>
<i>OCS >> POS</i>	-0,02	-0,69	0,49
<i>ACS >> POS</i>	0,95	27,10	0,00

Based on the regression analysis results, the β , T, and P-Value values were also found in this model. The outcome-based control system variable did not have a significant effect on perceived supervisor support. However, the activity-based control system was found to have a significant effect on perceived supervisor support ($\beta = 0.55$, $T = 6.55$, and $P\text{-Value} = 0.00$). This means that H4 is supported. The activity-based control system variable has a greater effect than the outcome-based control system on perceived supervisor support.

5. Hypothesis 5

Table 14. Hypothesis 5

	<i>R-Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig</i>
<i>AS</i>	0,34	25,23	0,00

The results of the R-square value regression analysis found that the capability-based control system had an adaptive selling value of 0.34, meaning that 12% of the adaptive selling variable was explained by this model. The F-value in this model is 25.23 with a significance level of 0.00. The capability-based control system variable has a significant influence on adaptive selling ($\beta = 0.48$, $T = 5.02$, and $P\text{-Value} = 0.00$).

Table 15. Hypothesis 5

	β	<i>T</i>	<i>P-Value</i>
<i>CCS >> AS</i>	0,48	5,02	0,00

In addition, researchers conducted an independent t-test analysis to determine the effect of the presence or absence of a capability-based control system on adaptive selling. Before conducting the analysis, researchers divided the sample into two groups: low capability-based control system (average CCS value < 3, n=43) and high capability-based control system (average CCS value > 3, n=6).

Table 16. T Test

Variabel	N	F	Levene Sig.	df	T	p-value sig.
<i>AS</i>	49	0,03	0,88	47	4,33	0,00

The results of the independent t-test showed a significant difference ($T = 4.33$, $P\text{-Value} = 0.00$) between the low capability-based control system group (average CCS value < 3, n=43) and the high capability-based control system group (average CCS value > 3, n=6) in terms of adaptive selling scores. This supports hypothesis H5.

6. Hypothesis 6

Table 17. Hypothesis 6

	<i>R-Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig</i>
<i>ASE</i>	0,53	56,04	0,00

The results of the R-square value regression analysis found that the capability-based control system had an analytical skill enhancement of 0.53, meaning that 28% of the analytical skill enhancement variable was explained by this model. The F-value in this model is 56.04 with a significance level of 0.00. The capability-based control system variable has a significant influence on analytical skill enhancement ($\beta = 0.63$, $T = 7.49$, and $P\text{-Value} = 0.00$).

Table 18. Hypothesis 7

	β	<i>T</i>	<i>P-Value</i>
<i>CCS >> ASE</i>	0,63	7,49	0,00

The researchers conducted an independent t-test analysis to determine the effect of the presence or absence of a capability-based control system on analytical skill enhancement. Before conducting the analysis, the researchers divided the participants into two groups: low capability-based control system (average CCS score < 3, n=43) and high capability-based control system (average CCS score > 3, n=6).

Table 19. T Test

Variabel	N	F	Levene Sig.	df	T	p-value sig.
<i>ASE</i>	49	0,11	0,73	47	6,50	0,00

The results of the independent t-test showed a significant difference ($T = 6.50$, $P\text{-Value} = 0.00$) between the low capability-based control system group (average CCS value < 3, n=43) and the high capability-based control system group (average CCS value > 3, n=6) in terms of analytical skill enhancement. This supports hypothesis H6.

CONCLUSION

The results of this study have several conclusions. Here are some of the conclusions found in this study:

1. The results show that the outcome-based control system has a greater influence than the activity-based control system on selling orientation at Hilti. The outcome-based control system variable has an influence on selling orientation. However, the activity-based control system variable does not have an influence on selling orientation.
2. The results of the study show that the activity-based control system has a greater influence than the outcome-based control system on customer orientation at Hilti. The activity-based control system variable has an influence on customer orientation. However, the outcome-based control system variable does not have an influence on customer orientation.
3. The results show that the activity-based control system has a greater influence than the outcome-based control system on perceived organizational support at Hilti. The activity-based control system variable has an influence on perceived organizational support. However, the outcome-based control system variable has no influence on perceived organizational support.
4. The results show that the activity-based control system has a greater influence than the outcome-based control system on perceived supervisor support at Hilti. The activity-based control system variable has an influence on perceived supervisor support. However, the outcome-based control system variable does not have an influence on perceived supervisor support.
5. The results show that the capability-based control system has an influence on adaptive selling at Hilti. The capability-based control system variable also has a significant difference with the low capability-based control system in adaptive selling.
6. The results show that the capability-based control system has an influence on analytical skill enhancement at Hilti. The high capability-based control system variable also has a significant difference with the low capability-based control system in analytical skill enhancement.

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